

THE INFLUENCE OF COLLECTIVE CREATIVE ACTIVITY ON THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A STUDENT'S PERSONAL QUALITIES

RAXIMOVA XAYRINISO ASLMUROD KIZI

2nd year student of majoring in foreign language,

Faculty of History and Philology

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

Scientific supervisor: MASALIMOVA ALINA MARATOVNA

Teacher of the Russian Language Department

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the influence of collective creative activity on the formation and development of a student's personal qualities in Russian language lessons. Collective creative activities are, first of all, the full-blooded life of the teacher and student, and at the same time, their common struggle to improve the life around them. In this life, in this struggle, teachers act as senior comrades to students, acting with them and ahead of them.

Currently, in socio-pedagogical theory and practice, much attention is paid to the use of active forms of training and education, since these forms contribute to the formation of an active life position and the education of a creative type of personality. Interest in this problem is also explained by the fact that in our difficult time of crises and changes, a person needs to learn to be prepared for any difficulties, be able to overcome them, and also be able to make decisions and take actions, that is, to show leadership qualities. This is especially true for students in their activities.

Modern students of this age are able to show initiative, activity, and creativity, but real practice suggests that in the vast majority of cases at a university, students passively carry out the instructions of the teacher, while the student is able to actively participate in public life and make decisions independently in various situations.

Initial learning of the Russian language lays the foundation for all further learning and personal development. The peculiarity of education and training at this level is that they are carried out, as a rule, by one teacher.

The social success of students in future, educational, personal, and professional activities depends on skillful leadership and the combination of various forms of work aimed at developing leadership qualities in students.

It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the implementation of these approaches should be carried out during joint activities by all members of the team, and therefore the development of students' leadership qualities should take place in collective activities.

Collective creative education is a special way of organizing the life activities of students and teachers, which involves joint activities aimed at improving life together. Collective creative work is the most important structural component of the methodology of collective creative education. This technique assumes the broad participation of everyone in the selection, development, conduct and analysis of collective cases. Everyone is given the opportunity to determine for themselves their share, the nature of their participation and responsibility. Collective creative activities make it possible to create a wide creative playing field in university lessons, which consists in the fact that each participant in the activity is in a situation of inventing, writing, imagining, that is, creating something new. In the process of collective creative work, students acquire communication skills, learn to work, share success and responsibility with others, and learn a lot of new things about each other.

Collective creative work

Thus, two important processes are taking place simultaneously - the formation and unity of the class team, and the formation of the student's personality, the development of certain personal qualities. In the process of common work, interaction between people of different ages occurs. During the planning and organization of a collective creative activity, teachers and students acquire extensive organizational experience; everyone can submit an idea, propose a new way of action, and take on the implementation of a certain stage of a collective creative activity. Collective creative work becomes a powerful force of attraction at the university and provides extensive extracurricular employment for students. Collective creative work, according to T.A. Stefanovskaya, enriching the team and the individual with socially valuable experience, allows everyone to demonstrate and improve the best human inclinations and abilities, needs and relationships, to grow morally and spiritually. The strength of each collective creative activity is that it requires a common search, gives it an impetus and opens up wide scope for it. Therefore, in each of these cases, a flexible form and rich, varied content, and non-standard options are important. In the field of education, collective activity and collective creative endeavors have occupied their special place for decades. This wonderful technique, a technology that perfectly takes into account psychology, is truly capable of working miracles. Everyone who immersed themselves in the enchanting atmosphere of the Communist gathering, participated in collective creative work, had their creative potential magically awakened, and the kindest feelings for their comrades arose.

Now collective creative activity is experiencing a rebirth of its diversity, and periodicity allows students to realize their interests and needs, develop intellectual and creative abilities, and social creativity. This system assumes the broad participation of everyone in the selection, development, conduct and analysis of collective cases. As you know, there are no ready-made recipes for education. It is impossible to repeat someone's original idea one to one. A collective creative work is impossible, but "grabbing" this idea, feeling it and developing it with schoolchildren in an updated version is already creativity. There are hundreds and thousands of models of working with students in Russian language lessons. Each has its own script, its own composition, its own editing, its own content, its own set of creative roles. What is important here is the idea of a collectively creative work. The very potential of a collective activity (in

which there are a lot of individual roles, positions, tasks, situations, findings) is rich in the collective thoughts of the guys. Student improvisation is the highest achievement. A collective creative endeavor. And everything turns out differently for everyone. Any model can be enriched with the content of different areas of educational activity. The main thing is that students find themselves, realize their potential in business, and get enough of the luxury of communication, community and co-creation.

When working with Collective Creative Affairs, the teacher constantly relies on micro-collectives: detachments, units, teams, councils, creative associations, friend groups, in order to reach everyone in one or another Collective Creative Affairs. Students can be in different microgroups at different stages of preparation, conduct and analysis. And this is very important. In different groups, teachers enter into new relationships and occupy new positions. Such techniques as drawing lots, counting, voluntary desire, and application for participation will help to divide the children into "action groups." Children can be "divided" into groups, according to playful and even comic signs: hair color, eye color, height, names, birthday, place of residence, etc. You can name the first three or four members of the group, they will choose one partner each, those chosen will name the next, and the team will quickly be completed. You can lay out colored circles, emblems and other "amulets", the children will choose them randomly, creating a group.

The group is the main "tool" of collective creative activities. Students must be taught to work together, respecting the opinion of each of their comrades, taking into account his interests and desires. If everyone wants to do something, you should use a competition, if no one wants a draw. Everyone is given the opportunity to determine for themselves their share, the nature of their participation and responsibility.

Collective creative activities make it possible to create a wide creative playing field, which consists in the fact that each student is in a situation of inventing, composing, imagining, i.e. creating something new. The result of such creativity is scripts, essays, poems, songs written by students individually or jointly, performances, miniatures, etc. are demonstrated on stage. Exhibitions, almost always organized during Collective Creative Affairs, showcase a wide range of creative works of an applied nature.

Large exhibitions of applied and written creativity, as well as public performances by students on stage in front of each other, often not just in front of peers from the same age. In the process of collective creative activities, students acquire communication skills, learn to work in a team, share success and responsibility with others, learn a lot of new things about each other, and finally, simply get to know each other and make friends. In the process of common work, people of different ages interact, the older ones help the younger ones, the younger ones learn from the older ones. Collective creative activities become a powerful force and provide extensive extracurricular employment for students. A positive emotional attitude, a guaranteed situation of success, releases good feelings and empathy from everyone to everyone.

Collective creative activities make it possible to create a wide creative playing field at the university, which consists in the fact that each participant in the activity is in a situation of inventing, composing, imagining, that is, creating something new. In the process of collective creative work, students acquire communication skills, learn to work, share success and responsibility with others, and learn a lot of new things about each other. Thus, two important processes are taking place simultaneously - the formation and unity of the class team, and the

formation of the student's personality, the development of certain personal qualities. Collective creative activities allow students to realize their interests and needs, develop intellectual and creative abilities, and social creativity. This system assumes the broad participation of everyone in the selection, development, conduct and analysis of collective cases. Thus, collective creative activities are the right way to connect and create a university community for a long time, creating and expanding a space conducive to personal development.

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